

Cultural and Spiritual Adaptations to Extreme Weather Events of Ethnic Farming Communities of the Three Watersheds Situated at Different Altitudinal Locations along Agno River Basin, Benguet and Pangasinan, Philippines

Josel M. Florentin ✉

College of Forestry, Benguet State University, Philippines

Emerson V. Barcellano

College of Environmental Management and Forestry, Isabela State University, Philippines

Suggested Citation

Florentin, J.M., & Barcellano, E.V. (2024). Cultural and Spiritual Adaptations to Extreme Weather Events of Ethnic Farming Communities of the Three Watersheds Situated at Different Altitudinal Locations along Agno River Basin, Benguet and Pangasinan, Philippines. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 172-179. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).14](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).14)

Abstract:

Ethnic farming communities in Agno River Basin face climate stressors that threaten their agricultural production. This paper investigated and assessed the cultural/spiritual adaptations to climate variabilities and extremes of ethnic farming communities in Agno River Basin, Philippines. How the presence of these cultural/spiritual practices moderate or mitigate the effects of climate variabilities and extremes were likewise investigated.

The climate-related hazards considered in this study which are pronounced in the river basin are prolonged and extreme rainfall intensity, typhoons and extreme winds, drought, flood and occurrence of pests and diseases. These hazards are becoming more frequent and intense resulting to limited agricultural production. This paper considered only the sectors of agriculture/socioeconomic,

water and health.

The descriptive method employed in this study was based on the works of Oppenheimer et al (2014); Saroar, Routray and Leal Filho (2015) and Brooks and Adgers(undated). The data-gathering activities were household survey using pre-tested questionnaires, focused group discussions and key informant interviews. The ethnic affiliations of the farming communities were I-Karao, Ibaloi, Kankanaey and Kalanguya tribes. Secondary data on changing rainfall and erratic temperature characteristics were consistent with the general perception of the ethnic farming communities.

Cultural/ spiritual traditions of Ethnic farming communities in the Agno River Basin form part of their adaptations to climate extremes and variabilities. The greatest number of rituals and activities (5) such as childless couples raising plant materials, burning of rice straws and *Alay*, *Leppas*, *Maepdesan*, and *Ibkas* or *maboteng*. are dedicated to ensuring a good harvest. *Canyao*, *Libot*, and *Begnas* are undertaken to prevent the occurrence of hazards. On the other hand, *Ubob*, *Bayaniban*, and *Sakdo* are adaptations to mitigate the impact of climate extremes and variabilities. Both *Canyao* and *Leppas* are also thanksgiving activities while *Tagainep* or dream interpretation serves as a coping mechanism.

Keywords: *Agno River Basin, Ethnic farming communities, Cultural/ spiritual adaptations, extreme weather, climate-related hazards.*

Introduction

Studies show that agricultural yield will likely be severely affected over the next hundred years due to unprecedented rates of changes in the climate system (Thornton et al., 2011). Short-term climate-related disasters such as typhoons and landslides damage farming community's homes, equipment, and irrigation infrastructure (FAO 2021; d' Errico, undated). These continuing impacts remain to pose threat on food security. Agriculture, particularly crop production, depends on relatively consistent weather patterns from year to year. (Mase, A. S., Gramig, B.M., Prokopy, L. S., 2017). Correspondingly, studies comparing the exposures to extreme climatic variations of farming communities located at different altitudes, with different ethnic affiliations and spiritual beliefs within the same watershed ecosystems is wanting. Different farming communities may have unique populations living in distinct environmental conditions. Therefore, said communities may have different levels of exposures to various types of natural hazards, and their coping strategies also differ in response to the different climatic abnormalities (Garcia, J.N.M, Wagan A.M. & Medina S.M., 2016). This information gap creates a need to examine the differences in the exposures to extreme climate variabilities of farming communities located at different altitudinal levels in the same watershed and/or river basin including their ethnic affiliations and cultural and spiritual adaptive capacities.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on the three watershed components (Ambuklao, Binga and San Roque) of the Agno River Basin (ARB). They are located at different altitudinal locations: Ambuklao (758 masl), Binga (563 masl), and San Roque (295 masl) (Figure 1).

Physical and biological information of the river basin were characterized. Exposures to climate stressors can best be assessed by the direct impact it has on the various dimensions of

community life (LEAD Pakistan, 2017). Adhering to this premise, exposures to climate-related stressors of farming communities and their cultural and spiritual adaptive mechanisms were assessed using a bottom-up approach and participatory rural appraisal. The method aims to solicit detailed information from ethnic farming communities about the complexity of threats and their unique ways of adaptation which are not ordinarily captured in literatures and other previous studies. It works on the belief that local knowledge is unique to a culture or community and it denotes a type of knowledge that has evolved within the community and has been passed from one generation to another. As such, ethnic communities are considered as experts of their environment, particularly where they have maintained their traditional livelihoods and subsistence economies. (Mendoza, et al. 2014).

Figure 1. Map Depicting the Location of the Three Watersheds along Agno River Basin, Philippines

Farming communities in the three study watersheds were represented by focused communities with distinct ethnic identities. These are I-Karao tribe in Ambuklao, Ibaloi Tribe in Binga, and Kalanguya-Ilocano in San Roque. They were identified and pre-selected based on their historical affinity with the watersheds. The I-Karao are indigenous to the Ambuklao watershed. Their settlement is located nearest to the watershed. They are known to be a closed

community and as such, have preserved their cultural practices in all aspects of life.

The Ibaloi tribe in Binga watershed are also indigenous to the area. They are said to be the pioneers of the place. However, they were forced to move to higher grounds when the Binga dam was constructed. Their knowledge of the history of their community is extensive.

Likewise, the *Kalanguyas* of San Roque are the indigenous and pioneering community of the place.

The number of respondents paralleled with the represented watershed area. Based on the percentage of the total area, sixty (60) percent, twenty-five (25) percent and fifteen (15) percent represented Ambuklao, Binga and San Roque, respectively. Totaling to 230 respondents, 138 respondents were from Ambuklao, while San Roque and Binga were represented by 58 and 34 respondents, respectively. Permission was sought from the National Commission on Indigenous People (NCIP) before the conduct of interviews.

Aside from one-on-one interviews with the farmers, Key Informant Interviews (KII) and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) were conducted. Participants belonged to different groups and stakeholders who are knowledgeable of their area of expertise. They provided historical accounts about their cultural, spiritual, environmental, agricultural and other practices and necessary information as well as experiences on past climate-related stressors.

The first part of the questionnaire gathered information on the socioeconomic profile that include income and income sources, farm ownership, farming experiences, food consumption, information and technology awareness, and awareness of benefits derived from watersheds. The second part assessed their exposures to climate-related stressors and their cultural and spiritual adaptive mechanisms. The known cultural and spiritual adaptations were assessed based on the number of farmers who are knowledgeable, number of farmers adopted and implementing. The farmers were also asked regarding the effectivity and the reasons for not

adopting/implementing despite that they are knowledgeable of the cultural and spiritual remedies.

Results

Climatic Type

Based on the Modified Coronas Classification System, Agno River Basin is under climate type 1. The river basin experiences dry season from November to the latter part of May while the wet season is experienced during the rest of the year with a maximum rainfall from June to September (NAPOCOR, 2016).

Rainfall Pattern and Occurrences

Rainfall in the basin is naturally orographic. The four months period between June to September account for 70 to 80 percent of the annual rainfall. The north to northwest monsoon and the east trade winds carries little rain. The area with lowest rainfall can be observed along the river valley upstream of Ambuklao Dam where rainfall averaged about 2,400 mm/year. Rainfall increases steadily in both flows of the drainage basin way from the riverbed and exceed 3,000 mm/year at some areas in the basin (NAPOCOR, 2016). The average annual rainfall recorded by PAGASA is 3891.54 mm covering a 30-year period (1985-2014) and the minimum and maximum mean rainfalls during wet season are 344.75 mm and 950.43 mm respectively (PAG-ASA, 2016).

Topography

Generally, the service area of the watershed starts at the lowland plains with a gradient ranging from zero to 18 percent or level areas. Slope gradient starts slowly to rise from these areas until it reaches a slope of 18 percent.

From an altitude of 100 masl (Figure 2), the topography of the upland watershed begins to become rugged, characterized by irregularly patterned relief of ridges, canyons and peaks.

Figure 2. Slope Map of the Three Watersheds within Agno River Basin

There are no extensive valleys in the three study watersheds, but stretches of narrow depressions apparently exist. The highest peak or mountain range (Mount Pulag) with an elevation of 2,922 masl is located at the boundary of Benguet and Ifugao. The lowest elevation of 100 masl is at the discharge point of the Agno River at San Manuel, Pangasinan (DENR Undated Report)

Vegetative Cover

There is a progressive deterioration of the vegetative cover of the river basin in the downstream direction all the way to the mouth of the canyon of San Roque. The primary forest cover has practically disappeared except at some isolated spots at some elevations and along gullies and stream banks. Mossy forests and a few stands of Benguet Pine trees still dominate the top of higher ridges while dipterocarp species abound in lower elevations. A great portion of the basin is open land, which is covered primarily with cogon grass (*Imperata cylindrica*).

Respondents' Profile

Significant variations in ethnicity were observed (Table 1) as the respondents in Ambuklao were all Karao but none in Binga and San Roque. Almost all and most of those in San Roque and Binga, respectively were Ibaloi. One in every five respondents in San Roque and only three respondents in Binga were Kalanguya.

Nine in every 10 respondents were born and raised in the areas of study. Almost all those in Ambuklao and around two-thirds of those in San Roque and Binga claimed being natives of the place.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents by Ethnicity

VARIABLES	Ambuklao (n=138)		Binga (n=34)		San Roque (n=58)		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Ethnicity								
Karao	138	100	0	0	0	0	138	60
Ibaloi	0	0	30	87	11	19	76	33
Kalanguya	0	0	3	8	45	77	12	5
Others	0	0	2	5	3	4	5	2
					X ² c= 181.76 p=0.00**			

Majority (51%) of the respondents indicated using indigenous farming systems or techniques,

this did not significantly differ from the 49% who said they do not do so (Table 2).

Table 2. Percent of Respondents Using Indigenous Farming Systems

Variables	Ambuklao		Binga		San Roque		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Practice of Indigenous Farming Techniques								
No	76	55.07	17	50	24	41.38	117	50.87
Yes	62	44.93	17	50	34	58.62	113	49.13
$X^2c = 9.01$ $p=0.06^{ns}$								

Climate-Related Stressors

The climate-related hazards considered in this study which are pronounced in the river basin are prolonged and extreme rainfall intensity, typhoons and extreme winds, drought, flood and occurrence of pests and diseases (Table 3). These hazards are consistent with the data from Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA-DOST, 2018) that they are becoming more frequent and intense resulting to limited agricultural production.

Exposures

The farming communities’ exposure to climate-related hazards were variable with averages of moderate for Ambuklao, and rare for both Binga

and San Roque, respectively. The overall average exposure to hazards of the whole Agno River Basin was however estimated as rare. The differences, however, has an average P-value of 0.386 which indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at 5 percent level of confidence. However, for flood hazard, result of the same statistical test revealed that Binga and San Roque watersheds have average scores categorized as rare while very rare score was noted for Ambuklao watershed. Consistent with this result are the average scores for flood-producing hazard prolonged and extreme rainfall intensity for the three watersheds. This complementing result is that despite statistically not significant scores, score for Ambuklao is higher (2.6) than Binga and San Roque with identical scores of 2.0.

Table 3. Average Exposures Scores

Hazards	Ambuklao	Binga	San Roque	P value
Prolonged and extreme rainfall intensity	2.6	2.0	2.0	0.441 ^{ns}
Typhoons and extreme winds	2.2	2.8	2.2	0.441 ^{ns}
Drought	2.2	2.2	2.2	0.543 ^{ns}
Flood	2.2	1.2	1.8	0.441 ^{ns}
Pests and Diseases	1.6	1.0	0.8	0.459 ^{ns}
Average	2.16	1.84	1.80	0.386^{ns}
Description	Moderate	Rare	Rare	

Table (Table 3) revealed that hazards typhoons and extreme winds and drought have statistically similar scores for the three watersheds which are considered having medium exposure.

The same table yields that hazard pests and diseases posted the lowest average score among the considered hazards for all the watersheds. However, for purposes of comparison, their average scores revealed that they are categorized as rare for both Ambuklao and Binga and very rare for San Roque.

Cultural and Spiritual Adaptive Capacities

Results revealed that ethnic farming communities in the river basin have different cultural and spiritual strategies to adjust to the effect of climate-related hazards.

Cultural and spiritual traditions in the Agno River Basin form part of their adaptations to climate-related hazards. The greatest number of rituals and activities such as childless couples raising plant materials, burning of rice straws and

Alay, *Leppas*, *Maepdesan*, and *Ibkas* or *maboteng*, are dedicated to ensuring a good harvest (Table 4). Likewise, *Canyao*, *Libot*, and *Begnas* are

undertaken to prevent the occurrence of hazards.

Table 4. Cultural and Spiritual Beliefs of the Ethnic Farming Communities

Cultural and spiritual traditions	Beliefs
Childless couples responsible for raising plant materials; burning of old rice straws; <i>Alay</i> , <i>Canyao</i> , <i>Leppas</i> , <i>Maepdesan</i> and <i>Ibkas</i>	To ensure good harvest
<i>Canyao</i> , <i>Libot</i> and <i>Begnas</i>	To prevent the occurrence of hazards
<i>Ubob</i> , <i>Bayaniban</i> , <i>Sakdo</i>	To mitigate the impact of climate-related hazards
<i>Canyao</i> , <i>Leppas</i>	Thanksgiving activities
<i>Tagaineḡ</i>	Forecasting climate-related hazards

The same table revealed that *Ubob*, *Bayaniban*, and *Sakdo* are adaptations to mitigate the impact of climate extremes and variabilities. Both *Canyao* and *Leppas* are also thanksgiving activities while *Tagaineḡ* or dream interpretation serves as a coping mechanism.

Discussion

The results depicted that there are dissimilarities on the residents' cultural/spiritual strategies to adjust to the impacts of climate-related hazards.

The local residents and in Ambuklao are found to show cultural adaptation through their traditional practices, e.g. *canyao* with 100 percent adaptation. The purpose is to plead for better crop production (e.g. agricultural crops could be prevented from pests and diseases infestations, and for successful endeavors). Although they claimed that there are no scientific bases for these practices, there are still ethnic farmers who believe in the effectiveness of such activities.

In the three watersheds, there are other cultural beliefs practiced to ensure crops/products grown could support food requirements such as childless couples should be tasked or responsible for nursery raising plant materials. Likewise, cultural and spiritual practices that include burning of old rice straws; *Alay*, *Canyao*, *Leppas*, *Maepdesan* and *Ibkas* are undertaken to ensure plentiful harvests. On the other hand, the conduct of *Canyao*, *Libot* and *Begnas* activities are believed to prevent the occurrence of hazards and *Tagaineḡ* is to forecast the occurrence of the hazards. *Ubob*, *Bayaniban* and *Sakdo* are expected

to mitigate the impact of climate-related hazards and *Canyao* and *Leppas* are activities as thanksgiving for abundant harvest.

These are remnants of the animism religion of the early Filipinos. While the dominant religious group is that of Roman Catholic, upland farmers and other local residents have linkage with different religious denominations. All these are supportive of adaptation strategies to moderate harm/risk and exploit beneficial opportunities (Garcia, J.N.M, Wagan A.M. & Medina S.M., 2016, DENR-ERDB, DENR Climate Change Project, undated; Mallari, 2016; and Desjardins, 2013).

Conclusion

The findings of this study show that the key physical features of the three watersheds are similar, while the mean temperatures are 19.5 °C, 19.8 °C and 27.7 °C respectively and their corresponding mean annual rainfalls are 3,291 mm, 3,891mm and 3,232 mm, respectively. However, the altitudes of the three study watersheds showed some variations. Their mean elevations are 1,549 masl, 1,050 masl and 698 masl respectively.

The ethnic affiliations of the selected communities were I-Karao (Ambuklao), Ibaloi (Binga) and mixture of Ilocano, Kankanaey and Kalanguya tribes for San Roque watershed. Binga watershed is nearest to public facilities, while Ambuklao is the farthest from a city, hospital, and university. San Roque is farthest in terms of distance to elementary and high

schools, church and municipal halls. While the geographical locations which dictate the proximity of the watersheds to tertiary schools influenced their educational attainment.

The climate-related hazards identical for the three watersheds are prolonged and extreme rainfall intensity, typhoons and extreme winds, drought, flood and occurrence of pests and diseases.

The communities recognized the considered climate-related hazards and have practiced the long-established cultural and spiritual beliefs as their coping mechanisms to offset the hazards' impacts.

Their cultural and spiritual adaptations to climate-related hazards are dependent on their perceptions and experiences of the hazards. Moreover, limited experience, lack of access to information on climate-related hazards and deficiency of education influence their adaptation strategies.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the National Commission on Indigenous People (NCIP) and the hosts Local Government Units for allowing the conduct of interviews. Likewise, special mention to Feliciano G. Calora Jr., PhD., former president of Benguet State University, and Guillermo A. Mendoza, Associate Professor Emeritus at the University of Illinois for their valuable insights and comments. This work was supported in part by Benguet State University Scholarship Program.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

Department of Environment and Natural Resources. (n.d.). DENR Report. Retrieved from <https://denr.gov.ph/>

Department of Environment and Natural Resources. (n.d.). DENR Climate Change Project. Retrieved from <https://faspelib.denr.gov.ph/sites/default/files//LGIS/PHILCCAP%20LL%20BP%20SS.pdf>

Desjardins, Raymond. (2013). Climate Change—A Long-term Global Environmental Challenge. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 77, 247–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.03.084>

D'Errico, M. (n.d.). *Resilience Index Measurement and Analysis (RIMA) model*. Resilience Analysis and Policies team Agricultural Development Economics Division Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (2021). *The impact of disasters and crises on agriculture and food security*. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb3673en>

Garcia, J.N.M, Wagan A.M. & Medina S.M. (2016). *Vulnerability and Adaptive Capacity Assessment for Different Agroecosystems (VAST-Agro)*. Los Banos, Laguna, Philippines: Agricultural Systems Cluster, CA-UP Los Banos.

LEAD, Pakistan. (2017). *Climate Change Assessment Methodology of Leadership for Environment and Development*.

Mallari, J. & Ezra, C.A. (2016). Climate Change Vulnerability Assessment in the Agriculture Sector: Typhoon Santi Experience. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 216, 440-451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SBSPRO.2015.12.058>

Mase, A.S., Gramig, B.M., & Prokopy, L.S. (2017). Climate change beliefs, risk perceptions, and adaptation behavior among Midwestern U.S. crop farmers. *Climate Risk Management*, 15, 8-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CRM.2016.11.004>

Mendoza, G.A., Macoun, P., Prabhu, R., Sukadri, D., Purnomo, H., & Hartanto, H. (2014). *Guidelines for Applying Multi-Criteria Analysis to the Assessment of Criteria and Indicators*. Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR), Jakarta 10065, Indonesia.

National Power Corporation (NAPOCOR). (2016). Annual Report. Retrieved from [https://www.napocor.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/Transparency Seal/Reports/Annual Reports/2016 NPC Annual Report.pdf](https://www.napocor.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/Transparency%20Seal/Reports/Annual%20Reports/2016%20NPC%20Annual%20Report.pdf)

Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration, Department of Science and Technology (PAGASA-DOST). (2018). *Climate Change in the*

Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.pagasa.dost.gov.ph/information/climate-change-in-the-philippines>

Thornton, P. K., Jones, P. G., Ericksen, P. J., & Challinor, A. J. (2011). Agriculture and food systems in sub-Saharan Africa in a 4°C+ world. *Philosophical transactions. Series A, Mathematical, physical, and engineering sciences*, 369(1934), 117–136. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2010.0246>